

Relationship Between Coastal Hydro-Morphological Terrain and Maritime Crime Incidences in The Niger Delta Basin of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Little wonder criminality thrives: riverine terrain challenges access, hence, criminal elements exploit hydro-morphological features of the terrain to operate in Nigeria's Niger Delta. This study examines the potential impact of hydro-morphological characteristics on maritime crime incidents in the Niger Delta Basin of Nigeria. Landsat and Shuttle Radar Topography Mission-Digital Elevation Model data from the United States Geological Survey Earth Explorer website were used to analyze the hydro-morphological features of the terrain. Analytical Hierarchy Process and weighted overlay analysis within Microsoft Excel and ArcGIS Pro version 3.1, respectively, was utilized to map potential maritime crime zone areas. The findings were that the study area's gentle slopes (0° to 2.66°), plains (50.72%), low elevation (65.41%), and water bodies (4.47%), promote waterlogging and floods, facilitating maritime crime. Findings revealed that 24,906.10 km² and 613.21km² of the study area were identified as potential high-risk and very high-risk areas for maritime crime incidents, respectively. These areas represented 38.66% and 0.95% of the total study area. The study concludes that hydro-morphological features significantly impact maritime crime occurrence, influencing areas prone to potential maritime crime incidents. The study recommended the need to prioritize security in the potentially high-risk maritime crime zones areas and oil spill hotspots with robust protocols and compliance measures.

Keywords: *Hydro-morphological Features, Hydrological Events, Floods, Maritime Crime, Niger Delta*

Introduction

The spatial dimension of crime has gained increasing importance in criminological and geographic research, especially concerning how physical and ecological characteristics influence criminal activity patterns. Traditional maritime crime studies have mainly centered on human behaviour, often overlooking environmental factors such as elevation, water bodies, and vegetation that shape the patterns of crime opportunities (Breetzke, 2012; Otto, 2015; Szabolcs, 2024) at coastal areas. Landforms including elevation, slope, and geomorphic features impact where offenders choose to operate, thus influencing the spatial distribution of crime incidents (Curtis-ham & Bernasco, 2025). Research, for instance, has shown that

higher elevations correlate with reduced burglary risk whereas other terrain aspects like slope steepness might have limited effect (Breetzke, 2012). Beyond topography, hydrological processes like river flows, flooding, sediment transport, and drainage alter habitats and settlement patterns, indirectly affecting maritime crime incidence through changes in accessibility and cover. Such linkages are critical in sensitive environments like Nigeria's Niger Delta, where climate change and environmental degradation reshape the landscape with concomitant impacts on crime. Specifically, the Niger Delta, one of the world's largest wetlands and Africa's most extensive delta system, draws economic

significance from its abundant oil reserves and strategic coastal position (Ola et al., 2024; Zabbey et al., 2021). Historically, its intricate network of rivers and creeks facilitated trade and transport during the colonial era. However, since the discovery of crude oil in the 1950s, the region has experienced profound transformations. Oil exploitation has led to severe environmental degradation and heightened socio-economic inequalities, fueling tensions and criminal activities including oil theft, piracy, and pipeline vandalism that exploit the terrain's complexity (Nkemdirim & Biyignandam, 2024). The coincident environmental harm and socio-economic marginalization have established conditions favourable to increased maritime crime networks, challenging regional governance and security.

In this context, maritime crime encompasses illegal activities committed in territorial and international waters, ranging from piracy, sea robbery, smuggling, human trafficking, illegal fishing, to illicit tapping and theft of oil from pipelines (Sosnowski et al., 2024; United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC], 2023). In the Niger Delta context, the sprawling riverine and creek systems afford criminals strategic hideouts, facilitating rampantly reported piracy and sea robbery (Umoette, 2025). Oil bunkering represents a particularly lucrative crime driven by poverty and unemployment, exacerbating local and national security challenges (Ikonne, 2025; Paki & Dan-Woniowei, 2024). Furthermore, human trafficking and smuggling amplify vulnerabilities in coastal communities. These maritime crimes undermine both the economic stability of local livelihoods and Nigeria's broader maritime security framework by disrupting critical oil supply chains and sea routes.

Central to understanding this nexus is the concept of hydro-morphological terrain,

which blends hydrological processes, such as water flow, sediment transport, and flooding, with coastal geomorphology to form Nigeria's dynamic landscape (Cho et al., 2023; Solaun et al., 2025). In the Niger Delta, continuous sediment deposition, river braiding, and tidal influences create complex mosaics of natural levees, channels, floodplains, and wetlands (Abam & Fubara, 2022). The Niger Delta's hydrological regime features high annual rainfall variability (2700 to 4000 mm) and mixed tidal and fluvial flow patterns, contributing to seasonal flooding and sedimentation cycles (Edokpa et al., 2025). Human activities including urbanization, dam construction, land-use changes disrupt natural hydrological connectivity and escalate flood and erosion risks, altering aquatic and terrestrial habitats (O'Farrell et al., 2025; Odoh et al., 2024). Such hydro-morphological complexities form spatial environments where stagnant waters and intricate waterways provide operational advantages and hideouts for maritime criminals engaging in piracy and illegal refining (Abam & Fubara, 2022; Amangabara & Onyewuchi, 2021). Hence, the hydro-morphological terrain both shapes and is shaped by the socio-economic, political, and security ecologies of the Niger Delta.

Despite advances in geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing for delineating hydro-morphological features and crime clusters (Abdulkadir, 2016; Jeffery et al., 2024), there remains a gap in specifically linking these physical characteristics with maritime crime patterns in this region. Globally, morphometric and hydrological indices such as basin area, drainage density, slope, and runoff potential are widely utilized for landscape characterization and environmental risk assessments including flooding and erosion (Kabite & Gessesse, 2018; Shekar & Mathew, 2024). In the Niger Delta's complex

geo-ecological context, spatial analytic tools reveal critical terrain features and socio-economic vulnerabilities germane to understanding the intricate crime landscape (Joab-peterside et al., 2021). There is thus an urgent need for integrated spatial and environmental assessments that incorporate hydro-morphological terrain alongside socio-economic and climatic factors to inform tailored governance and resource security interventions tailored to the region's unique context.

Furthermore, environmental criminology has emphasized how geographic features influence spatial decision-making of offenders, with physical attributes like elevation and land cover mediating crime risk and diffusion (Breetzke, 2012; Sypion-Dutkowska & Leitner, 2017). Sypion-Dutkowska & Leitner (2017) demonstrated that elevated or rugged terrain often presents lower crime opportunities, while features such as water bodies exhibit dual roles as barriers or conduits. Complementing this, climatic variables such as seasonal rainfall, temperature extremes, and humidity further modulate crime levels through behavioural and economic impacts (Heo et al., 2025; Schutte et al., 2021). For example, temperature increases have been correlated with rises in violent crime in multiple contexts (Schutte et al., 2021). Together, these environmental factors underscore the complex interplay of ecological and socio-economic influences underpinning maritime crime in the Niger Delta.

In addition, studies of the Niger Delta revealed a deeply intertwined problem of the nature of the hydro-morphological terrain, environmental degradation, socio-political marginalization, governance deficits, and the emergence of maritime crime syndicates (Ehiane, 2025; Erondu & Nwakanma, 2025). These structural inequities are exacerbated by ineffective resource management, corruption, and insufficient community involvement

(Ajala, 2015; Elisha & Gbaranbiri, 2024). Criminal syndicates exploit this fragile governance pattern and the challenging terrain to perpetuate maritime crime. While government agencies have initiated projects to curb environmental harm and improve security (Bode-obanla & Ajisebiyayo, 2025), poor coordination and lack of stakeholder participation have limited their success (Eheazu & Ph, 2023). Consequently, comprehensive governance frameworks incorporating community involvement and human security principles are needed to address the persistent maritime crime challenges.

This study emerges against this complex backdrop, aiming to examine the relationships between hydro-morphological terrain features and associated coastal hazards and maritime crime incidences in the Niger Delta Basin of Nigeria, with the broader goal of informing integrated, sustainable management and governance frameworks that could enhance security, environmental resilience, and socio-economic development. The objectives are to analyze the effect of hydro-morphological parameters and identify potential areas prone to maritime crime incidents in the Niger Delta Basin of Nigeria.

Material And Methods

The Study Area

The study area spans approximately 69,219 km² and is located between latitudes 4°11'4"N and 7°2'54"N and longitudes 4°50'24"E and 9°35'4"E, bordered by Nigerian states to the north, Cameroon to the east, the Atlantic Ocean to the south, and Ondo State to the west (Figure 1). The region is predominantly riverine and flood-prone, especially in Bayelsa and Rivers. It has an equatorial climate with temperatures from 25°C to 34°C and receives 2,700–4,000 mm of annual rainfall, mostly during the April–

October wet season (Abam & Fubara, 2022).
Gas flaring and high humidity (80%)

exacerbate temperatures and discomfort,
impacting local socio-economic

Figure 1: The Study Area

conditions. Hydrologically, the area features a multilayered aquifer system within the Benin Formation and a dense network of rivers and creeks shaped by heavy rainfall and tidal influences, resulting in swampy conditions and frequent flooding that disrupt agriculture and urban centers like Port Harcourt. Vegetation includes rainforests, freshwater swamps, and Africa’s largest mangrove ecosystems, which buffer erosion

Methods

This section describes the methodological framework used to analyze the hydro-morphological terrain characteristics of the Niger Delta Basin, Nigeria, and their relationship with maritime crime incidents. Figure 2 shows the data types analytically procedure employed to determine the potential crime zones. While the data acquired from Key Informant Interviews

but face threats from climate change and habitat loss. Geological formations rich in oil underpin extensive reserves but also environmental degradation, contributing to socio-economic challenges and fueling maritime crime amid a population of approximately 38 million confronted with environmental and infrastructural pressures (Phil-Eze et al., 2021)

(KIIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were used to validate the model.

The study examines hydro-morphological parameters known to influence human activity and environmental conditions relevant to maritime crime. Key topographic features analyzed include elevation, slope, aspect, curvature, drainage density, and land use/land cover (LULC) types, selected based on their established role in spatial crime variation (Doring et al., 2024). The incorporation of the Topographic Position

Index (TPI) and Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) further enhances the understanding of landform dynamics and hydrological processes, which can potentially facilitate criminal movement and concealment (Al-sababhah, 2023; Avand et al., 2022). Spatial datasets were analyzed using ESRI's ArcGIS Pro version 3.1. Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Digital Elevation Model (SRTM-DEM) data was preprocessed by applying Wang & Liu (2006) sink-filling algorithm to ensure hydrological consistency before deriving terrain attributes. Slope, calculated via partial derivatives of elevation with respect to the x and y axes, was converted from radians to degrees using the factor 57.29578 and reclassified into five categories from very low to very high, representing terrain steepness.

Elevation data, expressed as meters above sea level, and distance to the nearest river were derived and analyzed alongside drainage density (Dd). Dd was computed as the ratio of total channel length to basin area, to characterize watershed connectivity. Curvature analysis classified surface shapes into convex, concave, and flat, informing flood susceptibility assessment. TPI was calculated to classify landforms by measuring the difference between elevation at a focal cell and the average elevation of neighbouring cells within a 30 m radius (Al-sababhah, 2023). Positive TPI values indicate ridges, negatives indicate valleys, and values near zero designate flat terrain (Skentos, 2018). Landform classes followed Weiss (2001) taxonomy, with the area of each class quantified by multiplying cell counts by cell size and normalizing by total study area, facilitating proportionate spatial representation. TWI mapping also leveraged SRTM-DEM and hydrological flow tools to characterize spatial wetness distribution, an indicator of soil moisture and potential water accumulation zones affecting vegetation density and shelter availability for maritime

criminals (Avand et al., 2022). The TWI calculation applies the formula

$$TWI = \ln \left(\frac{a}{\tan \beta} \right)$$
, where a is the upslope contributing area per unit contour length and β is the local slope in radians. Hydrological preprocessing included sink filling, flow direction, and flow accumulation.

LULC categories like built-up areas, sandy/bare ground, mangroves, vegetation, and water bodies were encompassed to evaluate urban sprawl impacts on maritime crime. The 2024 LULC map was generated and analyzed in ArcGIS Pro 3.1, with polygon areas converted to percentage. This approach aligns with prior Nigerian urban studies focusing on coastal areas (Fatai, 2021).

To identify potential maritime crime hotspots, hydro-morphological variables were integrated using the Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP), a structured multi-criteria decision-making method based on Saaty's (1977) pairwise comparison matrix. The study included eight parameters including elevation, slope, curvature, distance to river, drainage density, TPI, TWI, and LULC classes weighted according to their relative influence on vulnerability and crime occurrence, consistent with approaches in environmental susceptibility and maritime crime risk assessments.

An 8×8 pairwise comparison matrix was developed using Microsoft Excel to assign relative importance scores from Saaty's fundamental 1–9 scale (Saaty, 2008). The matrix elements were reciprocals for inverse comparisons, ensuring mathematical consistency (Saaty, 1987). The weights for each factor were computed as normalized eigenvectors from the matrix, with consistency ratio (CR) checks conducted to validate the reliability of judgments, adopting thresholds where CR < 0.1 is acceptable. The consistency index (CI) was calculated

as $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max}-n}{n-1}$, where λ_{max} is the largest eigenvalue of the matrix and n the matrix size.

Figure 2: The Methodology used for Maritime Crime Risk Zones Mapping

The weighted layers were integrated through spatial weighted overlay analysis in ArcGIS Pro 3.1, normalizing raster values to a common scale and multiplying each by their assigned AHP-derived weights. This method produced a composite maritime crime risk index map, reflecting localized environmental and socioeconomic susceptibilities. The approach has been successfully applied in analogous spatial analyses of hazard and crime susceptibility. All geospatial processing leveraged ArcGIS Pro version 3.1, with workflow detailed in Figure 2. The methodology encompasses DEM processing, terrain attribute derivation, thematic layer development, AHP weighting,

and final risk mapping, offering a comprehensive framework for hydro-morphological influence on maritime crime susceptibility in the Niger Delta.

Purposive sampling was used to select 10 key informants, two per state, across the five Niger Delta states for KIIs, focusing on experienced stakeholders with regional knowledge of maritime crime patterns. FGDs were held in Rivers and Bayelsa states due to their vulnerable, flood-prone coastal terrain characterized by estuaries, mangroves, and riverine systems that influence maritime crime dynamics. Respondents shared insights on how hydro-morphological features impact crimes like piracy, oil bunkering, and

kidnapping. KIIs and FGDs were manually transcribed to preserve local dialect nuances, then coded and thematically analyzed using grounded theory. Findings highlighted that the complex waterways provide both concealment and challenges, facilitating crime while hindering enforcement. These qualitative data validated the crime occurrence model in the absence of geocoded crime records, emphasizing integrated environmental and security interventions.

Results and Discussion

Describing the Hydro-Morphological Characteristics of the Study Area

Slope Analysis: The Niger Delta landscape exhibits substantial variation in slope, a key factor influencing both physical accessibility and hydrological processes relevant to crime patterns. Criminals tend to prefer flat terrain for easier movement and escape, making slope a critical variable (Odoh et al., 2024). Slope was classified into five categories based on degrees, ranging from 0° to 84.83° (Figure 3a). The largest class ($0-2.661^\circ$), representing 48.97% of the study area ($31,683 \text{ km}^2$), consists of flat terrain that promotes groundwater recharge via slow water movement but increases flood risk by

reducing runoff efficiency. Moderate slopes ($2.662-6.654^\circ$), covers 45.35% ($29,343 \text{ km}^2$), support agriculture but still face drainage and erosion challenges. Steeper slopes ($>24.952^\circ$), constitute only 0.21%, induce localized runoff and erosion issues that can exacerbate flooding (Table 1). Together, gentle slopes dominate (94%), highlighting the area's susceptibility to sediment deposition and flood hazards, which can affect crime incidence by enabling easier criminal access after flood events.

Curvature Analysis. Curvature quantifies surface convexity or concavity. Findings in Figure 3b revealed values ranged from -102.67 (highly concave valleys) to 100.56 (highly convex ridges). Concave areas promote water accumulation, forming wetlands prone to flooding and social disruption which could increase crime vulnerability. Flatter terrain with low curvature supports agriculture but can suffer from flooding if unregulated. Steeper convex surfaces drain quickly but are susceptible to erosion, influencing sediment transport. These rugged zones could provide militants and criminals with natural refuges, hindering law enforcement efforts and facilitating activities such as piracy and oil theft.

Figure 3: (a). Slope, (b). Curvature (c). Elevation and (d). Topographic Position Index (TPI)
Source: Authors’ Analysis (2025)

Elevation Analysis: Elevation variation in the Niger Delta reflects geological processes and sediment depositional environments. Findings revealed in Figure 3c and Table 2 revealed that 65.41% of the study area lies within low elevation zones of -78 to 44 m above sea level, particularly within Bayelsa, parts of Delta, and Rivers States. These low-lying floodplains facilitate biodiversity but suffer frequent flooding, undermining agricultural productivity and law enforcement presence, thereby facilitating criminal activity. Higher elevations (>1,068 m) cover only 0.31% of the landscape, mainly in Cross River State. These areas

present less flooding risk and lower maritime crime incidence. This findings aligns with those of Efiang et al. (2021), who reported that Cross River state exhibits elevation values between 0 and 1880 meters above mean sea level. Low elevation and flooding exacerbate social disarray, increasing crimes such as piracy, theft, and kidnapping during flood events when law enforcement is stretched thin. Additionally, the Niger Delta’s complex waterway network provides criminals with escape routes, complicating security efforts.

Table 1: Slope and Elevation Range and Area Cover of the Study Area

Grid Code	Classes	Area Covered (Km2)	Percentage of Study Area Covered
Slope (Degrees)			
1	0 – 2.661	31,682.76	48.97
2	2.662 - 6.654	29,343.31	45.35
3	6.655 - 13.972	2,647.41	4.09
4	13.973 – 24.951	885.92	1.37
5	24.952 – 84.833	138.01	0.21
	Total	64,697.41	100
Elevation (m)			
1	-78 - 44	42,359.50	65.41
2	44.001 - 108	9,925.93	15.33
3	108.001 - 198	8,427.30	13.01
4	198.001 - 364	2,621.90	4.05
5	364.001 - 639	8,52.94	1.32
6	639.001 - 1,068	370.48	0.57
7	1,068.001 - 1,896	201.53	0.31
	Total	64,759.58	100

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Topographic Position Index and Landform Classification: The TPI analysis quantifies terrain position relative to surrounding elevation, distinguishing ridges, valleys, and plains. Finding in Figure 3d and Table 2 revealed that TPI values ranged from -293.29 (valleys) to 578.66 (ridges). Landform classification. Both flat and open areas are prone to flooding and waterlogging, creating environments conducive to crimes like piracy, land grabbing, and illegal logging. Valleys cover 11.11% of the landscape and often harbour communities reliant on agriculture and fishing. Economic deprivation here correlates with increased crime, and remoteness could offers criminal hideouts. Canyons and incised streams (0.04%) present law enforcement challenges

due to ruggedness, fostering oil theft and smuggling. The sedimentary geology, dominated by sandstones and shales (Agbada and Akata formations), contributes to the terrain ruggedness in high ridge areas primarily in Cross River State

Distance to River Analysis: Proximity to rivers directly affects terrain vulnerability and accessibility for maritime crime. Figure 4a displays a gradient from highly vulnerable low-lying areas (<0.0146 km) near rivers to higher elevation, flood-resistant zones (>0.0844 km) further afield. Close river proximity encourages piracy and attacks due to operational ease and escape options, whereas increased distance lowers direct attack risk but remains socially susceptible due to economic stress.

Table 2: Landforms Classification based on TPI Values

S/No	TPI Values	Landform Classification	Cell Count	Area Covered (Km ²)	Percent of Area Covered
1	-293.29 - -29.995	Canyons, incised Streams	24,717	23.88186	0.03688
2	-29.994 - -16.318	Mid-slope Drainages	218,698	211.30857	0.32630
3	-16.317 - -6.059	Upland Drainages	1,990,230	1,922.98357	2.96941
4	-6.058 - -2.64	Valleys	7,446,232	7,194.63671	11.10974
5	-2.639 - 0.779	Plains	33,993,819	32,845.22669	50.71858
6	0.78 - 4.199	Open Slopes	18,597,988	17,969.59417	27.74809
7	4.2 - 14.457	Upper Slopes	4,355,086	4,207.93518	6.49776
8	14.458 - 28.135	Local Ridges	339,323	327.85786	0.50627
9	28.136 - 164.911	Mid-slope Ridges	58,251	56.28280	0.08691
10	164.912 - 578.66	High Ridges	42	0.04058	0.00006
Total			67,024,386	64,759.74799	100

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Drainage Density Analysis. Drainage density, the total length of rivers per unit area, influences hydrology and socio-economic conditions (Alam et al., 2020). Findings in Figure 4b shows the classification ranged from very low (0–6.679) to very high (26.717–33.395). High drainage density regions (urban/agricultural hubs) exhibit more organized economic activities and usually face different crime profiles compared to low-medium density zones where flood-driven economic hardships stimulate opportunistic crimes such as boat and oil theft, piracy, and armed robbery.

Topographic Wetness Index Analysis. TWI reflects spatial soil moisture and saturation derived from terrain and hydrological modeling. Twi could influence crime by affecting land usability and concealment opportunities. Findings in Figure 4c shows areas with high TWI values, typically flat and

wet lowlands, are resource-rich but flood-prone, thus vulnerable to illegal activities such as oil theft and illegal fishing. Conversely, steep areas with low TWI have lower soil moisture and reduced crime incentive.

Land Use and Land Cover: Figure 4d shows the LULC map of the study area. Findings in Figure 4d and Table 3 show a landscape dominated by vegetation (61.02%), built-up areas (22.25%), and mangroves (10.6%), with water bodies and barren lands occupying smaller proportions. As noted by Eyoh & Okwuashi (2016), the LULC trends indicate that vegetation cover is declining largely due to urbanization, a process linked to increased competition for resources and socio-economic disparity, which may elevate maritime criminal activities including piracy and oil theft.

Figure 4: Map of (a). distance to river, (b). drainage density (c). TWI (d). LULC Types
Source: Authors’ Analysis (2025)

Table 3: Spatial Extent and Percentage of LULC Types of the Study Area

S/No	LULC TYPES	Area Covered (Km ²)	Percent of Area Covered
1	Water bodies	2,897.222	4.47
2	Vegetation	39,514.9	61.02
3	Mangrove	6,873.132	10.61
4	Built-Up	14,406.43	22.25
5	Sandy, barren, rocky stony waste	1,068.039	1.65
	Total	64,759.723	100.00

Source: Authors’ Analysis (2025)

Potential Areas of Maritime Crime Incidents in the Niger Delta Basin of Nigeria

Relative Criteria Weight Assessment

The study employed AHP to evaluate flood, hydrological and maritime crime-influencing factors by assigning relative scores and

performing pairwise comparisons. In evaluating hydrological factors that influence maritime crime incidents, various weights were assigned based on their influence. Eight parameters were assessed for their impact on environmental and socioeconomic activities. Table 4 shows the pair-wise interaction matrix for AHP based potential area of

maritime crime occurrence while Table 5 displays the weights of normalized potential maritime crime incidents. As shown in Table 4, TWI and elevation were assigned the least priority due to their complementary roles in basin hydrology. TWI was given higher importance than TPI and slope because it models wet conditions more comprehensively, combining aspects like slope and contributing area. TWI was also considered more influential than curvature for predicting saturated areas, but equally important as LULC types when assessing different facets of hydrology. Drainage density, though crucial for water movement, was balanced with TWI in influence due to their complementary nature. These evaluations helped prioritize factors based on their relative impacts on flood dynamics within the study area's hydrological context. Elevation was given a higher value than slope due to its broader impact on basin-scale processes like precipitation distribution and evapotranspiration rates. Drainage density had more direct influence over hydrological processes than TPI, but both were considered complementary rather than one being more influential. Distance to rivers was prioritized over elevation for maritime crime assessment because proximity to waterways facilitates access for illegal activities. For maritime crime analysis, LULC types were highly valued as they directly relate to socio-economic conditions conducive to criminal environments near waterways. Curvature, though not directly linked to maritime crimes, was considered for its impact on access routes near waterways. Slope and drainage density had indirect links unless affecting local economic conditions or access routes. Overall, these assignments reflect the complex interplay between hydrological factors and their relevance to maritime crime dynamics in areas with significant waterway connectivity. Table 5 further indicates the consistency and reliability of the assessment.

With eight factors ($n = 8$) considered, the maximum eigenvalue ($\lambda_{\max} = 10.35$) is used to calculate the CI (0.04), which measures the deviation from perfect consistency. This CI is then normalized by the RCI (1.41) to produce the CR (0.028). A CR of 0.028 is well below the commonly accepted threshold of 0.10 which suggests that the judgments and weights assigned to the various factors influencing maritime crime incidents are acceptably consistent, indicating a reliable assessment framework. Table 6 presents a multi-criteria analysis for identifying potential areas of maritime crime incidence in the study area in ArcGIS Pro version 3.1 environment. This analysis integrates the various factors considered in this study. The parameters were reclassified using the class Table 6 which helps in understanding how these different environmental and spatial factors contribute to maritime crime risks. The reclassification process involves categorizing each factor into distinct classes based on their potential impact on maritime crime occurrence. For instance, TWI is crucial for predicting saturated areas that might influence access routes or hideouts for criminal activities. TPI provides insights into topographic features that could facilitate or hinder criminal operations. Distance to rivers is significant as it affects accessibility for illegal activities near waterways. LULC types are important because they reflect socio-economic conditions and land use patterns that can either foster or deter criminal environments. This multi-criteria approach allows researchers to evaluate how these factors interact and contribute to the overall risk of maritime crimes in specific regions, facilitating targeted interventions based on local conditions.

Table 4: AHP Pair-wise Interaction Matrix for Potential Areas of Maritime Crime Incidents

Factors	TWI	TPI	Elevation	Slope	Drainage Density	Distance to River	Curvature	LULC Types
TWI	1	3.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	4.00	2.00	1.00
TPI	0.33	1	0.33	0.50	0.25	0.14	1.00	1.00
Elevation	1.00	3.00	1	0.33	0.50	3.00	3.00	3.00
Slope	0.33	2.00	3.00	1	1.00	4.00	5.00	8.00
Drainage Density	1.00	4.00	2.00	1.00	1	5.00	1.00	5.00
Distance to River	0.25	7.00	0.33	0.25	0.20	1	0.33	4.00
Curvature	0.50	1.00	0.33	0.20	1.00	3.00	1	6.00
LULC Types	1.00	1.00	0.33	0.13	0.20	0.25	0.17	1
Sum	5.42	22.00	8.33	6.41	5.15	20.39	13.50	29.00

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Table 5: Weights of Normalized Potential Maritime Crime Incidents

Factors	TWI	TPI	Elevation	Slope	Drainage Density	Distance to River	Curvature	LULC Types	Average	Lambda
TWI	0.18	0.14	0.12	0.47	0.19	0.20	0.15	0.03	0.19	10.19
TPI	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.01	0.07	0.03	0.05	9.69
Elevation	0.18	0.14	0.12	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.22	0.10	0.13	10.11
Slope	0.06	0.09	0.36	0.16	0.19	0.20	0.37	0.28	0.21	10.35
Drainage Density	0.18	0.18	0.24	0.16	0.19	0.25	0.07	0.17	0.18	10.05
Distance to River	0.05	0.32	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.14	0.09	9.64
Curvature	0.09	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.19	0.15	0.07	0.21	0.10	10.24
LULC Types	0.18	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.05	8.85
Sum	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-

Note: $n = 8$, $\lambda_{max} = 10.35$, $CI = 0.04$, $RCI = 1.41$, $CR = 0.028$

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Table 6: Multi-Criteria Analysis for Potential Areas of Maritime Crime Incidents

S/No	Maritime Crime Causative Criterion	Unit	Class	Susceptibility Class Ranges	Susceptibility Class Ratings	Weight (%)
1	TWI	Level	-10.5418 - -4.3658	Very low	1	19
			-4.3657 - -2.111	Low	2	
			-2.1109 - 0.4378	Medium	3	
			0.4379 - 3.5749	High	4	
			3.575 - 14.4565	Very high	5	
2	TPI	Level	-293.29 - -6.0594	Very high	5	5
			-6.0593 - -2.64	High	4	
			-2.6399 - 4.1988	Medium	3	
			4.1989 - 147.8141	Low	2	
			147.8142 - 578.66	Very low	1	
3	Elevation	Meter	-71 - 67.7059	Very high	5	13
			67.706 - 198.7059	High	4	
			198.706 - 453	Medium	3	
			453.0001 - 946.1765	Low	2	
			946.1766 - 1,894	Very low	1	
4	Slope	Degree	0 - 2.661	Very high	5	21
			2.662 - 6.654	High	4	
			6.655 - 13.972	Medium	3	
			13.973 - 24.951	Low	2	
			24.952 - 84.833	Very low	1	
5	Drainage density	Km ²	0 - 5.1074	Very low	1	18
			5.1075 - 9.9529	Low	2	
			9.953 - 14.2746	Medium	3	
			14.2747 - 19.2511	High	4	
			19.2512 - 33.3947	Very high	5	
6	Distance to River	meter	0 - 0.034	Very high	5	9
			0.035 - 0.067	High	4	
			0.068 - 0.101	Medium	3	
			0.102 - 0.135	Low	2	
			0.136 - 0.169	Very low	1	

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Table 6: Multi-Criteria Analysis for Potential Areas of Maritime Crime Incidents Cont'd

S/No	Maritime Crime Causative Criterion	Unit	Class	Susceptibility Class Ranges	Susceptibility Class Ratings	Weight (%)
7	Curvature	Level	-102.669 - -1.4335	Very high	5	10
			-1.4334 - -0.6364	High	4	
			-0.6363 - 0.1607	Medium	3	
			0.1608 - 1.755	Low	2	
			1.7551 - 100.5991	Very low	1	
8	LULC types	Km ²	Water Body	Very high	5	5
			Mangrove	High	4	
			Vegetation	Medium	3	
			Built up	Low	2	
			Sandy, barren, rocky stony waste	Very low	1	

Source: Authors' Analysis (2025)

Potential Maritime Crime Areas Mapping

The Niger Delta region is grappling with the escalating impacts of maritime crimes, including illegal oil refining, sea piracy, armed robbery, and bunkering. These activities not only result in significant property loss and human casualties but also contribute to environmental degradation. As shown in Figure 5, using eight key parameters identified potential maritime crime incident areas across five zones: very low, low, moderate, high, and very high risk. Areas with elevated terrain with quartzel to leaf green colours, showed a lower likelihood of maritime crime occurrence such as Obudu and Agbor regions, while urbanized central areas, of the study area, faced moderate to high risks due to flood susceptibility and socioeconomic challenges. The southern part of the Niger Delta around Burutu, Brass, Buguma/Opobo, Oron axis among others was found to be at the highest risk due to its dense concentration water bodies.

The Niger Delta region is a hotspot for maritime crimes, including piracy and armed robbery, which significantly impact its spatial extent. The area covered by potential

maritime crime incidents varies across different risk levels, as shown in Table 7. Very low risk areas cover only 146.01 km², accounting for about 0.23% of the total area. In contrast, low risk zones span approximately 3,464.09 km², making up about 5.38% of the study area. These areas are generally less prone to maritime crime due to their geographical features characterized with higher terrain with lesser water bodies.

The study area is predominantly categorized as moderate, high, or very high risk for maritime crime incidents. The moderate risk zone covers a significant area of approximately 35,300.73 km² (54.79%), while the high risk zone spans about 24,906.10 km² (38.66%). The smallest yet most critical segment is the very high risk zone at around 613.21 km² (0.95%). These areas are more prone to maritime crimes due to the difficult hydro-morphological conditions and socioeconomic challenges. These findings align with broader regional trends observed in the Gulf of Guinea by Okpuvwie (2021), where hotspots of maritime piracy are concentrated in specific

areas across Nigeria and neighboring countries like Benin, Togo, Guinea, and Cameroon. The concentration of these risks underscores the need for targeted

interventions to effectively mitigate maritime crime in these zones.

Figure 5: Potential Areas of Maritime Crime Incidents

Source: Authors’ Analysis (2025)

Table 7: Spatial Extent and Percentage of Potential Maritime Crime Incidents Areas

S/No	Maritime Crime Index	Count	Area Covered (Km ²)	Percent of Area Covered
1	Very low	151116	146.01	0.23
2	low	3585226	3,464.09	5.38
3	Moderate	36535195	35,300.73	54.79
4	High	25777061	24,906.10	38.66
5	Very High	634658	613.21	0.95
	Total	66683256	64,430.14	100

Source: Authors’ Analysis (2025)

Model Validation of Coastal Terrain and Maritime Crime

The findings from the map of the spatial pattern of potential maritime crime zones in the Niger Delta revealed significant overlaps within the region's complex hydrographic landscape. The oil spill incidents and other kinds of maritime crime types could cluster particularly along the dense waterways and creeks extending from Bonny Island through Ahoada to the Burutu axis in Delta State, aligning with these high-risk crime zones shown in Figure 5. This geographical correlation of increase maritime crime on low elevation and high rivers networks areas supports the findings of Fullpower & Oba (2024) who stated that environmental degradation such as persistent oil spills acts as a catalyst for increased criminality. As local communities face disrupted livelihoods due to environmental harm, engagement in illicit activities becomes a survival mechanism, exacerbated by the low-lying and intricate riverine networks in Bayelsa and Rivers states. Maritime crimes in the Nigeria's Niger Delta remain a critical security and socio-economic challenge, deeply intertwined with environmental degradation and local livelihoods because they occur in the areas with low elevation and more river networks. The complex hydro-morphology of the Niger Delta, characterized by labyrinthine waterways, creeks, and flood-prone lowlands, provides both concealment and access routes for criminal activities such as piracy, pipeline vandalism, and illegal oil refining. Respondents from affected communities link these crimes directly to environmental harm, with one from Bonny Island lamenting: The spillage in Bonny Island is so much. Just two weeks ago there was a spill near Cawthorne Channel. Yes, those areas have many rivers. That spillage destroyed vegetation and had impacted over ten communities which normally occur in the

communities closer to the sea. These spills devastate local ecosystems, fisheries, and farmlands, causing widespread livelihood disruptions and prompting urgent calls for government cleanup efforts that have so far been inadequate. Our boys damage oil facilities because they are hungry and unemployed.

This testimony reflects how environmental degradation fuels socio-economic grievances that drive maritime crime as a survival strategy. Bonny waterways and its environs have become hotspots for piracy and kidnapping, with recent incidents confirming an alarming trend. In early 2025, pirates abducted at least 12 passengers along the Isaka River in Rivers State, assaulting multiple boats and seizing goods (Lawal, 2025). Another attack in February targeted a passenger boat on the Bonny-Okrika waterway, resulting in multiple casualties and ongoing rescue efforts (ARC, 2025). The findings in this report corroborates with the potential maritime crime areas shown in Figure 9, where Bonny River, Escravos/Forcados River, offshore Brass, and the Delta creeks have been identified as major hotspots where maritime crime is particularly high. Security reports highlight that pirates exploit their intimate knowledge of local geography to evade naval patrols, conducting attacks up to 250 nautical miles offshore (ARC, 2025). In April 2025, a product tanker was boarded south of Nigeria's coast-the first such incident in four years-underscoring persistent risks despite improved crew preparedness (The Maritime Executive, 2025). These events illustrate the challenges maritime security agencies face in policing a vast and complex maritime domain, where pirates operate with impunity, often in collusion with local actors. The Nigerian Navy and maritime police are underfunded and ill-equipped, limiting their

capacity to protect vulnerable communities and commercial interests.

Economic marginalization and youth unemployment are central drivers of maritime crime in the Niger Delta. Many youths, including graduates, resort to illegal activities such as oil bunkering and pipeline vandalism due to lack of employment opportunities many of which are concentrated in the identified potential area. As many of our interlocutors in explained, There are numerous oil firms here, but hardly any of our people work there. Our boys damage oil facilities because they are hungry, unemployed and sometimes because of socio-political reasons.

Another noted: Pipeline vandalism attracts government attention, mostly in Rivers and Bayelsa State, even part of Delta state. Many youths in riverine areas die due to unemployment and poor infrastructure. In my state, piracy and kidnapping occur mainly from Bonny to Ahoada. Engaging youths and providing roads and hospitals in riverine communities is crucial to protect the environment and reduce crime.

These testimonies align with research showing that socio-economic deprivation, combined with environmental harm, creates cycles of poverty and criminal resistance (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime., 2021). Illegal refining persists despite its environmental damage because it provides a critical income source, though it also causes social divisions and health risks, as another participant observed: These activities cause waterborne diseases and damage farms, affecting mostly our parents who are

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study explores how the hydro-morphological terrain in Nigeria's Niger Delta Basin influences maritime crime. The region's geography, characterized by flat, low-lying areas prone to flooding, creates an environment conducive to criminal activities.

fishermen and farmers. It also causes social division, where some support the activity while others do not.

This complex socio-ecological dynamic demands integrated policies that address both environmental restoration and economic empowerment particularly at the potential areas of these crimes. To mitigate maritime crime and promote sustainable development, respondents call for urgent, holistic interventions that combine environmental protection, youth engagement, and improved governance. One participant urged: The government and oil companies should engage youths, provide employment, and involve us in protecting our environment.

Another emphasized: Security agencies should strengthen the protection of the environment to reduce maritime crime, which could cause reduction in "damaging" the area.

Such calls align with academic recommendations advocating multidimensional strategies integrating environmental rehabilitation, youth empowerment, and equitable resource governance to dismantle crime networks and promote long-term stability (Akpogheli et al., 2021). Enhancing maritime domain awareness through regional cooperation and increased funding for security forces is essential to counter piracy and kidnapping threats that jeopardize Nigeria's blue economy and maritime trade. The persistence of maritime insecurity, even amidst recent security improvements, highlights the urgency of these comprehensive approaches.

These areas provide access and cover for offenders, complicating law enforcement efforts. The study utilized GIS-based methods, integrating flood, hydrological, and socio-economic factors like LULC types to map potential maritime crime zones. The analysis identified five risk zones: very low, low, moderate, high, and very high. Moderate

and high-risk zones cover the majority of the study area, while the very high-risk zone, though small, is critical due to its heightened vulnerability. Areas around Burutu, Brass, Buguma/Opobo, Bonny Island, Ekeremor, and Oron exhibit the highest risk due to their dense network of waterways. The findings underscore the importance of understanding the terrain's influence on crime dynamics and highlight the need for targeted interventions to mitigate maritime crime effectively. By recognizing these factors, policymakers can develop more effective strategies to address the complex interplay of geography and socio-economic conditions driving maritime crime in the Niger Delta.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the interconnected challenges of the relationship between the Niger Delta's hydro-morphological terrain, and maritime crime incidents: It is crucial to prioritize the security of the identified potential high-risk areas for maritime crime, particularly those prone to piracy and armed robbery. Efforts should focus on implementing robust security protocols, including the deployment of armed guards and advanced surveillance systems like AI-Enabled ISTAR (Intelligence, Surveillance, Target Acquisition, and Reconnaissance) Systems and swamp drones. Additionally, collaboration with local naval forces and international partners is essential to ensure effective patrolling and rapid response capabilities in these hotspots. This proactive approach will help mitigate risks associated with maritime crimes and protect vessels operating in these regions. Also, the hydro-morphological analysis underscores the impact of terrain characteristics on crime incidence, particularly in flood-prone, low-lying areas. Prioritizing investments in infrastructure improvements, such as robust drainage systems and flood defenses, is essential to mitigate environmental hazards

and associated criminal activities. State governments should collaborate with federal agencies responsible for disaster management and urban planning to enhance community safety and resilience.

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